

Behaviour of pre-engineered industrial structure with different bracings under various wind speeds and higher seismic zone considering larger openings

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Abstract

Steel structures consisting longer spans has become the need of any industrial structure which can be satisfied by constructing pre-engineered buildings (PEB). A considerable rise in PEB constructions is observed as they offer advantages like shorter erection time, economy, low maintenance etc. PEB consists typical roof, wall support, and structural frame that are manufactured in a factory wherein additional steel is eliminated using the tapered sections according to bending moment requirements. Studies have been carried out on behavior of PEB considering various bracings, considering specific seismic and wind zones. In this paper, analysis of PEB without and with diagonal and X bracing is performed using Staad-pro for larger openings to study its behavior for different wind speeds (viz., 33, 39, 44, 47, 50, 55m/s) and seismic zone V. Analysis results indicate that, the displacement of PEB exceeds permissible limits (IS:875-2015 Part-3) for wind speed above 44 m/s and demands use of bracings. When diagonal and X-bracings are used, there is slight difference observed in the displacements of PEB. Further, results indicate that, displacement of PEB with diagonal and X-bracings reduces by an average value of 35.05% for all wind speeds when compared over PEB without bracings. When compared to PEB without bracings, the values of base shear and support reactions of PEB with diagonal and X-bracings rise by an average of 5.07% and 6.40%, respectively. The study concludes that, for the wind speeds 50m/s and 55m/s significant increase in the values of displacement, base shear and support reactions occurs.

Keywords— Pre-engineered buildings, seismic zones, wind zones, types of bracings, large openings.

1.0 Introduction

In the present modern construction age, steel is considered as the most widely used material because of its many beneficial qualities, including developed strength, evolved flexibility, optimal cost, dependability, durability, and recyclability. The steel productions are growing rapidly throughout the world because of the increased use of steel structures. Steel buildings have several benefits, including quick construction and the ability to accommodate large spans and heavy loads. Furthermore, steel buildings can withstand earthquakes better than concrete ones (Sharma et al., 2021). The conventional steel buildings (CSB) are typically built with trusses and are made from hot-rolled structural elements that are readily accessible on the market. Mostly, the CSB are constructed using market-available steel sections which may not be suitable for construction on account of not meeting the design requirements because of their larger sectional sizes or properties. Furthermore, despite the fact that the tensions in these steel sections change throughout their length, their cross-sections remain constant. Because of this, the structure's overall weight increases, necessitating the provision of massive footings for such buildings (Bharmal et al., 2023). The PEB requires creating a frame geometry that closely aligns with the bending moment diagram, which aids in improving the amount of steel used and reducing the structure's overall weight (Varma & Chandak, 2022). Therefore, in accordance with the bending moment diagram, the components or members in the PEB may have cross-sections that vary throughout their length. A PEB is a kind of structure where the components are formed and assembled in a factory, and at the construction site, bolted connections are utilized to unite them (Rahman, 2023). PEB are steel structures made up of stiff frames, bracing members, and secondary structural members made of cold-formed steel that have metal sheets covering the roof and external walls. Due to many beneficial qualities of PEB viz., cost-effective, energy-efficient, lesser weight, quicker erection, etc. they are more popular in the recent years (Tale & Vasugi, 2019).

1.1 Components of PEB

Primary, secondary, and a few auxiliary members make up the PEB components. The primary members are the hot-rolled steel sections, which are formed into columns and rafters that often have tapered geometries. Secondary members include grits and purlins which are often cold-formed sections. The members that fall under the category of auxiliary members include sheets, gutters and other accessories. The PEB structure and its constituent parts are depicted in Figure 1 (Gawade & Waghe, 2018).

Fig.1 Prefabricated building and components

(Source: <https://civildigital.com/pre-engineered-buildings-peb-components-advantages-design-methodology>)

1.2 Concept of openings

The buildings consisting less than 5% openings in the walls are defined as enclosed buildings. When the percentage of openings falls between 5% and 20%, the building is classified as moderately enclosed. When the proportion of opening surpasses 20%, the building is referred to as an exposed building. The building's opening condition is determined by the opening area as a proportion of the gross sheeted area. In the analysis of industrial steel structures, it is essential to consider the inner as well as external wind pressures as per the provisions of IS:875-2015 (Part 3). The degree to which the cladding allows air to pass through it determines the internal air pressure in an industrial structure. Based on the direction of the air flow relative to the building's openings, the interior air pressure might be either positive or negative. As per the clause 7.3.2.1 of IS:875-2015 (Part 3) it is stated that when constructing a building with cladding that allows air to pass through small area openings (less than 5% of building's total opening area), but no large openings, it is crucial to take the possibility of positive or negative internal air pressure into account. Consequently, two conditions, one with an internal pressure coefficient of +0.2 and another with an external pressure coefficient of -0.2 are involved in the design calculations. Further, as per the IS: code 875-2015 (Part 3) clause 7.3.2.2 it is stated that the buildings with large openings (i.e., opening greater than 20% of the wall area) are classified under open buildings (IS:875-2015 Part 3).

2.0 Literature review

The research papers that have been published by several researchers for studying the behaviour of PEB structures are rigorously reviewed and are presented in the following section.

Rao and Vishwanath (2014) have performed comparative analysis and design of PEB and CSB structures in Staad pro software with dynamic forces (including wind forces) and medium size openings (i.e., 5% area of openings). The responses of the PEB and CSB viz., bending moment, shear force and support reactions are determined by software analysis. According to the study's findings, when compared to equivalent CSB values, the bending moment, shear force, and support reactions of PEB decrease by 4.96%, 21.5%, and 21.3%, respectively. Further, a reduction of 36% in the steel quantity is found in PEB as compared to CSB. The study concludes that the PEB are advantageous over CSB in reducing structural responses and also contribute in material and cost savings.

Somasekharan and Vasugi (2017) have analyzed and designed PEB and CSB using SAP 2000-18 software considering different sections viz., Indian standard angle, universal beam, universal column, and square hollow for determining the most economical chord section for truss based on the values of deflection. The analysis of PEB and CSB along with V, X, K and diagonal bracings was then performed to determine most economical chord section for truss considering dead, live, wind loads and assuming medium area openings (i.e., 20%). The results indicate that the PEB with K type of bracings contributes in the maximum reduction of deflection by 5.83% when equated to the deflection of CSB. The study concluded that PEB with bracing of type K performs well when compared with CSB with regard to the economic feasibility.

Bhadoria and Pathak (2017) have performed a comparative analysis of PEB and CSB considering varying spans ranging from 10m to 50m with an interval of 10m. The analysis of PEB and CSB for different spans viz., 10m, 20m, 30m, 40m, and 50m is carried out in Staad pro consisting of dead, live, wind, seismic loads including with medium size openings (i.e., 5 to 20%). The analysis results for the weight and cost parameters for the structures (i.e., PEB and CSB) are compared in view of finding the economic structure. The results indicates that the cost and weight of the PEB and CSB structures decreases as the span increases. Further, the weight of the PEB structure is seen to be decreased by typical value of 30%, when associated over the weight of CSB. The investigation found that when compared to the CSB construction, the PEB structure is more inexpensive.

Tale and Vasugi, (2019) compared the PEB and CSB structures to ascertain the reactions with various bracing configurations, including X, K, diagonal, alternating diagonal, and inverted V-type. Further, the weight of the structures is also determined. Using staad pro software, the PEB and CSB analyses were performed with varying loads and medium-sized (i.e., 5–20%) apertures. According to the study, base shear and displacement values decrease by (16.94%) and (43.18%) respectively for the PEB with V-type bracings when equated with matching values of CSB. However, The natural period for PEB increases by 36% with V-type bracings. The concludes that the performance of CSB and PEB structures gets improved when these structures are provided with V-type of bracings.

Sai et al. (2021) conducted a performance comparison analysis for PEB on structural responses with different bay systems under the wind zones of two different locations, i.e. Vijayawada and Hyderabad. Using Stade Pro software, the PEB was evaluated and constructed with wind and seismic forces taken into account, assuming medium-sized openings (i.e., 5 to 20%) to calculate responses like shear force (SF) and bending moment (BM). The geometrical properties of the PEB components are selected in order to determine the weight of the structures, taking into account the magnitudes of SF and BM of the PEB components as determined by the software analysis. According to the study's findings, the overall weight of the Hyderabad-based construction is 11.04% less than the Vijayawada-based PEB structure. The findings indicate that the sectional sizes and structural weight of the PEB components are influenced by wind speed and seismic zones.

Ali Kaveh et al. performs study to employs Enhanced Colliding Bodies Optimization (ECBO) for achieving optimal design for three gable frames featuring tapered members. The design process adheres to AISC specifications, ensuring constraints related to stress, displacement, and stability are met. The weight of each gable frame is calculated based on the cross-sectional properties of its members. Through the optimization algorithms, the optimal weights are determined, with the cross-sectional properties and design constraints serving as variables and constraints, respectively. Additionally, a comparative analysis between Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Colliding Bodies Optimization (CBO) with ECBO is conducted to underscore the significance of the enhanced optimization technique.

3.0 PEB analysis

Using Staad Pro software, the analysis of a PEB without any bracing is carried out by taking into account the geometrical specifications as listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Geometrical specifications of PEB structures

Parameters	Details
Layout of the structure (size)	80 m × 30 m
Eave's level height	9 m
Sheets for roofing and side walls	GI sheets
Columns and principal rafters	Tapered I section purlins
Girts of wall and bracings	Cold formed channel section
Support type	Fixed
Soil type	Medium
Speed of winds	33,39,44,47,50,55 m/s
Type of seismic zone	Zone V
Openings percentage	>20% (large)

Considering the geometrical specifications (Table 1), the step wise analysis of PEB without and with consideration of different types of bracing is performed using staad pro. The following are the steps involved in the analysis of PEB structure.

1. Creating the PEB 2D portal frame and allocating supports
2. Defining sectional properties
3. Defining the loads
4. Applying loads on 2D PEB frame
5. Converting the 2D portal frame into 3D PEB frame

A. Analysis of PEB without bracing

The analysis of PEB without the bracings is performed by adopting the following steps:

Step 1: Creating the PEB 2D portal frame and allocating supports

Taking into account the geometrical specifications of PEB (Table 1) and guidelines given in IS: 800-2007 for roof slope, a 2D frame considering fixed supports to its columns is created and is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 PEB 2-D frame

Step 2: Defining sectional properties

Different sections are allocated to the various members of the 2D PEB frame as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2 Sections for PEB

Sr.No.	PEB member	Section type	Size (m)			
1	Column	Tapered I section	Section depth at start node	0.600		
			Web thickness	0.005		
			Section depth at end node	0.500		
					Top flange width	0.400
					Top flange thickness	0.014
					Bottom flange width	0.300
					Bottom flange thickness	0.014
2	Principal rafter	Tapered I section	Section depth at start node	0.8		
			Web thickness	0.0055		
			Section depth at end node	0.2		
			Top flange width	0.400		
			Web thickness	0.014		
			Section depth at end node	0.300		
			Top flange width	0.014		

Step 3: Defining the loads

The various loads consider for the analysis of PEB include seismic loads (SL), wind loads (WL), live loads (LL), and dead loads (DL) and the details of same are given below.

Dead load (DL)

A uniformly distributed load (UDL) that is transferred from secondary members to primary members makes up the dead load. In accordance with guidelines given in IS:875-(Part 1), a total load of 25kg/m² (0.25kN/m²) has been taken into account for the analysis.

Calculations of DL on rafters: The total DL transferred to the rafter from secondary members is calculated below:

- Weight of roof sheets: 0.15 kN/m²
- Weight due to solar panels, ducts, etc.: 0.10 kN/m²
- Total load: 0.25 kN/m²

Thus, the total load on the rafter is determined as:

$$\text{Load on rafter} = \text{Total load} = 25 \text{ kg/m}^2 \\ = 25 \text{ kg/m}^2 (0.25 \text{ kN/m}^2)$$

Live load (LL)

The loads resulting from workers movements (such as during maintenance operations), equipment, and materials comprise the live load (LL). In accordance with guidelines given in IS:875-(Part 2), the total LL of 75kg/m² (0.75kN/m²) has been taken into consideration for the analysis.

Wind load (WL)

The WL computations are carried out for each terrain category in accordance with the guidelines given in IS:875-2015 (Part 3) considering internal coefficient pressure (Cpi) as ± 0.7 applicable for to open structure (i.e., the structure with openings >20%).

WL operating on the main rafters

According to clause 7.3.3.2 IS:875-2015 (Part 3), Table 6, for determining the WL acting on the PEB rafters, the external pressure coefficients (Cpe) for a 1/10 roof slope and wind angles of 0° and 90° are considered. The WL acting on the rafters of PEB for a maximum wind speed of 55m/s is determined as per the calculations presented below.

i. Basic wind speed (V_b)= 55m/sec

ii. Determination of design wind speed

$$\text{Design wind speed (V}_z\text{)} = V_b \times K_1 \times K_2 \times K_3 \quad (\text{Clause 6.3})$$

where,

V_b, Basic wind speed = 55m/s

K₁, Probability factor (risk coefficient) =1.0 (Clause 6.3.1)

K₂, Terrain, height, and structure size factor=0.91 (Clause 6.3.2)

K₃, Topography factor =1.0 (Clause 6.3.3)

K₄, Importance factor for cyclonic region=1.15 (Clause 6.3.4)

Thus, $V_z = V_b \times K_1 \times K_2 \times K_3 = 55 \times 1.0 \times 0.91 \times 1.0 \times 1.15$

$$V_z = 57.56 \text{ m/sec}$$

iii. Design Wind Pressure (P_z) = 0.6 V_z² = 0.6 (57.557)² (Clause 7.2)

$$P_z = 1987.71 \text{ N/m}^2$$

Therefore, Pd= K_d x K_a x K_c x P_z

where,

K_d, Wind directionality =0.9 (Clause 7.2.1)

K_a, Area averaging factor =0.8 (Clause 7.2.2)

K_c, combination factor = 0.9 (Clause 7.3.3.13)

Thus, $P_d = K_d \times K_a \times K_c \times P_z = 1987.71 \times 0.9 \times 0.8 \times 0.9$

$$P_d = 1288.04 \text{ N/m}^2 = 1.28 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

iv. Determination of wind load

The wind load acting on the rafter is calculated using the formula (Clause 7.3.1 of IS:875) given below

$$\text{Wind load} = (C_{pe} \pm C_{pi}) \times P_d \times \text{bay spacing}$$

where,

C_{pe}= External pressure coefficient,

C_{pi}= Internal pressure coefficient,

P_d= Design wind pressure.

The values of external pressure coefficient (Cpe) and internal pressure coefficient (Cpi) are worked out for different wind angles (0° and 90°) for determining the wind load acting on rafters and are given in Table 3.

Table 3 External load acting on PEB rafters for maximum wind speed

Wind angle	0°		90°	
	EF	GH	EG	FH
Roof portion				
External pressure coeff. (Cpe)	-1.2	-0.4	-0.8	-0.6
Positive internal pressure coeff. (+ Cpi)	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
Negative internal pressure coeff. (- Cpi)	-0.7	-0.7	-0.7	-0.7
Net positive pressure coeff. (C _{pnet}) = (Cpe+Cpi)	-0.24	0.3	-0.1	0.27
Net negative pressure coeff. (C _{pnet}) = (Cpe-Cpi)	-1.64	-1.1	-1.5	-1.12
Maximum value of C _{pnet}	-1.64	-1.1	-1.5	-1.12
Area of openings (A), m ²	219.18	219.18	219.18	219.18
Wind load (F), kN/m	-2.27	2.80	-0.93	2.54

Thus, the total WL acting on rafters for wind angle ‘0’ and for roof portion ‘EF’ is calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Wind load (WL)} &= (C_{pe} \pm C_{pi}) \times P_d \times \text{bay spacing} \\ &= (-0.9426 + 0.7) \times 1.28 \text{ kN/m}^2 \times 7.27\text{m} \\ &= -2.27 \text{ kN/m} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the wind load calculations are performed for different wind speeds considering different roof portions (i.e., GH, EG, and FH) and are tabulated in Table 4.

Table 4 Wind loads acting on PEB rafters for different wind speeds

Wind angle		Wind speeds (m/s)					
		33	39	44	47	50	55
0	EF	-0.81	-1.142	-1.453	-1.658	-1.877	-2.20
	GH	1.011	1.412	1.797	2.051	2.321	2.80
90	EG	-0.337	-0.470	-0.599	-0.683	-0.773	0.93
	FH	0.915	1.278	1.627	1.857	2.101	2.54

Seismic load (SL)

The medium-type soil and seismic zone V have been taken into consideration for PEB analysis . As per the guidelines of IS:1893-2016 (Part 1 and 2) seismic loading on PEB structure is carried out. The design seismic load (V_b) is determined as per the formula given in IS:1893.

$$V_b = A_h W$$

where, ' A_h ' is the design horizontal seismic coefficient and ' W ' is the seismic weight of the structure. The design horizontal coefficient (A_h) is determined by using the following formula

$$A_h = \frac{\left(\frac{Z}{2}\right) \left(\frac{S_a}{g}\right)}{\left(\frac{R}{I}\right)},$$

where, $Z = 0.36$, seismic zone factor as per Table 3 of IS: 1893. $S_a/g = 2.5$, design acceleration coefficient for the medium type of soil. $R =$ Response reduction factor. $I = 1.2$, importance factor of the structure.

$$\text{Thus, } A_h = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) (2.5)}{\left(\frac{R}{I}\right)} = 0.27 \text{ and } V_b = 0.27 \times 1.29 = 0.35 \text{ kN/m}$$

Total load on PEB rafters (2D frame)

The total load (i.e., DL, LL, WL, and SL) carried by the PEB rafters is as given below
 $DL = 0.25 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Table 5 Total load on rafters

Type of bracing	Load over rafter, kN/m^2 (for 0^0 wind angle)	Load over rafter, kN/m^2 (for 90^0 wind angle)
Dead load	0.25	0.25
Live load	0.75	0.75
Wind load	-0.27	-0.93
Seismic load	0.35	0.35
Total load, kN/m	1.08	0.42

Step 4: Assignment of loads on PEB rafters (2D frame)

Staad Pro is used to perform the analysis once the loads from the previous steps are applied to the rafters of the 2D PEB frame. Table 5 displays the findings of the analysis for the reactions, including wind displacement. Table 6 shows that the 2D PEB frame's wind displacement responses does not fall inside the limits given by IS:800-2007 and IS:1893 (Part 1):2016 for the wind speed above 44m/s without bracings. Therefore, the provisions appropriate bracings should be included for the structure.

Table 6 Results of the PEB (2D frame) analysis

Re	Without bracings						Diagonal bracing						X-bracings					
	V						V						V					
	33	39	44	47	50	55	33	39	44	47	50	55	33	39	44	47	50	55
D, mm	2.17	126.5	161	172	201	294	15	75	130	156	160	164	13	74	130	154	159	162

Limiting value for displacement as per (IS:800-2007) given by the formula is $\text{Span} / 180$, which comes out to be 166.667 mm for the proposed structure.

Fig.3 3D view of PEB structures

Step 5: Conversion of 2D frame into 3D PEB structure

After assignment of loads to the rafters of 2D PEB frame, the conversion of 2D frame into 3D PEB structure is performed by using the ‘translation repeat command’ of Staad pro. After converting 2D frame into 3D PEB structure all the essential components of the structure (viz. purlins, wall girts, and bracings) are provided (Fig. 3) in order to carry out the analysis of the structure. Thus, the analysis of the structure is carried out for determining the responses viz., displacements, base shear, and support reactions. Additionally, the weight of the structure is determined.

4.0 Results and Discussions

Table 7 displays the findings of the Staad Pro software analysis of the PEB structure with X and diagonal types of bracings for the responses (Re.) of displacement (D), support reactions (Sr), base shear (Vb), and overall weight (W).

Table 7 Results of the PEB structural analysis

Responses	PEB Without bracing					
	Zone V					
	33	39	44	47	50	55
D, mm	62.18	126.50	161.52	172.09	201.80	294.51
Vb, kN	64.6	64.6	67.5	71.6	74.8	76.6
Sr, kN	227.1	227.1	227.1	228.4	237.1	239.8
W, kN	744.0	744.0	752.5	835.4	888.4	922.4
	PEB with Diagonal bracing					
	Zone V					
	33	39	44	47	50	55
D, mm	15.8	75.1	131.0	156.1	160.7	164.8
Vb, kN	67.6	67.6	67.6	72.7	74.9	87.1
Sr, kN	228.4	228.1	228.4	229.7	238.3	254.8
W, kN	754.3	754.3	754.8	754.9	890.4	1116.1
	PEB with X bracing					
	Zone V					
	33	39	44	47	50	55
D, mm	13.1	74.2	130.2	154.1	163.7	165.2
Vb, kN	67.9	67.7	67.9	73.0	76.8	92.4
Sr, kN	229.6	229.6	229.6	230.0	240.8	262.8
W, kN	759.4	759.4	760.0	761.7	925.5	1214.4

Referring to Table 6, variation in the values of displacements, base shear and support reactions for the PEB without and with bracings (viz., X and diagonal) considering seismic zone 5 is shown in Fig. 4 and 5.

Fig.4 Variation in displacements of PEB without and with bracings for seismic zone V

From Fig.4 it is observed that the displacement values of PEB without bracings increases by an average value of 45.15% upto wind speeds 44m/sec. Further, it is observed that for the wind speed higher than 47m/sec, the displacement values of PEB without bracings reaches to their maximum permissible limit (span/180) and thus the structure needs to be provided with appropriate type of bracings. Fig.4 also show the variation in the values of displacement for PEB provided with X and diagonal type of bracings from which it is observed that the displacement values of PEB with X and diagonal type of bracings get reduced by an average value of 35.50% and 34% respectively, when compared over the corresponding displacement values of PEB without bracing. Fig. 5 shows the variation in the values of base shear for the PEB without and with X and diagonal type of bracings.

Fig.5 Base shear of PEB with different bracings for seismic zone V

From Fig.5 it is observed that the base shear values of PEB without bracings increases with an average rate of 3.5% for all the wind speeds under consideration. For PEB with diagonal and X type of bracings, small increase (5.03%) in the base shear values are observed for wind speeds from 33 to 50m/sec. However, a significant increase (5.7%) in the values of the base shear occurs for wind speed above 50m/sec. The average increase in base shear for PEB with diagonal and X bracings is found to be 4.13% and 6%, respectively, in comparison to PEB without bracings. Fig.6 and 7 shows a variation in the values of support reaction and weight of the structure, respectively.

Fig.6 Support reactions of PEB with different bracings for seismic zone V

Fig.7 Steel quantity for PEB with different bracings for seismic zone V

The average percentage increase in support reactions is 1.51% and 2.52% for PEB with diagonal and X bracing respectively, and average percentage increase in overall weight is 4.2% and 8.60% for PEB with diagonal and X bracing respectively, when compared with the PEB without bracings.

Though, a reduction in the displacement's values of PEB with X and diagonal type of bracings occurs when compared over PEB without bracings (average 35%), no significant variation in the displacement values of PEB with X and diagonal type of bracings is observed (1.5%).

5.0 Conclusions

The following are the conclusions drawn from analysis of PEB structures:

1. The displacements of PEB without bracings increases by an average value of 45.15% upto wind speeds of 44m/sec and reaches to their maximum permissible limits (span/180) for the wind speeds higher than 47m/sec. This results into the structure's demand for the use of appropriate type of bracings.
2. The displacements of PEB provided with diagonal and X bracings gets reduced by an average value of 35% when compared with the corresponding displacements of PEB without bracings. No significant variation in the displacements of PEB with diagonal and X bracings occurs (average 1.5%).
3. The average base shear for PEB without bracings is found to be 69.93 kN and it increases with an average rate of 3.5% for all the wind speeds under consideration. The average base shear for PEB with diagonal and X bracings is found to be more by 4.13% and 6% respectively when compared over the corresponding base shear values of PEB without bracings.
4. For PEB with diagonal and X type of bracings, the base shear values get increased by 5.03% for wind speeds from 33m/sec to 50m/sec, however, a significant increase (13.05%) in the base shear occurs for wind speed above 50m/sec.
5. The average value of support reactions of PEB with diagonal and X bracings found to be increased by 2.05% when compared over PEB without bracings. Also, the overall weight of PEB with bracings (i.e., diagonal and X) is found to be increased by an average value of 8.5% when compared with the PEB without bracings.

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Data availability The authors declare that data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper.

Declarations

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